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Exploring the Factors Influencing Purchasing Intention of Bangladeshi Consumers on E-Commerce Platform Daraz.com.bd

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Abstract

The e-Commerce sector has seen dramatic growth in Bangladesh since the early 2000s, although at the time the country lacked prevalent internet access with a reliable online transaction system. The Bangladesh Government is currently working on digitalizing the nation but the adoption rate of e-commerce is relatively low. This paper intends to comprehend the factors that influence the purchase intention of Bangladeshi consumers from the e-commerce platform Daraz.com.bd. The survey questionnaire was encased in an online link for respondents to complete and submit. The survey received 302 respondents' data. It was established that the respondents' socio-demographic profiles – genders, age groups, and education levels – exhibited a significant impact on online purchase intention. Trust and quality were not correlated to online purchase intention while privacy negatively affected the purchase intention. Price, delivery, returning policy, and social influence affect purchase intention positively. Interaction test results showed that the effects of privacy and price, privacy and quality, and delivery and social influence hurt the dependent variable. However, these factors discretely affected purchase intention positively. The interaction between privacy and social influence, and quality and social influence enhance one another to demonstrate a positive effect on purchase intention. The results might help the company understand and target its future consumers and create focused advertisements for them. Additionally, to enhance the purchase intention of Daraz.com.bd visitors, the company needs to focus on improving certain factors while keeping in mind the interaction effect.

Keywords: E-Commerce, Purchase Intention, Bangladesh, B2C, Daraz.com.bd

1. Introduction

1.1 E-commerce Industry in Bangladesh

E-commerce is a fast-expanding industry in Bangladesh influencing both domestic and international trade. Although the Bangladeshi government is putting in a lot of effort to digitalize the country and grow the business, e-commerce is not widely adopted in the country. With the introduction of 3G and 4G internet connections as well as the quick uptake of online purchasing, the Bangladeshi e-commerce sector was predicted to increase by 70% in

recent years. However, only 3.4% of Bangladesh's retail market is made up of e-commerce. Internet penetration is rising in Bangladesh, 40% of the population participates in the development of local e-commerce, F-commerce (small startup businesses conducting online business through Facebook pages), and e-grocery firms.

Business-to-customer (B2C) e-commerce is still in the initial stage and faces a multitude of problems. Among the top companies in the nation are the online marketplace Daraz, which is supported by Rocket Internet, and the e-retailer Pickaboo backed by Foxconn, Bagdoom, and Chaldal. Although the number of consumers has grown in recent years, consumers are still not used to online shopping. Regardless, e-commerce envisions a promising future in Bangladesh. Bangladesh has 99% geographical coverage in voice and data connectivity. Figure 1. shows the growth of internet subscribers in Bangladesh. According to the Bangladesh Telecommunication Regulatory Commission (BTRC), the total number of Internet Subscribers in Bangladesh reached 117.3 million at the end of May 2021 of which 9.8 million use broadband connections whereas the remaining are mobile internet users.

Figure 1: Reports of Internet Subscribers

Source: BTRC

The aim of this research is, therefore, to explore key factors that influence e-commerce purchase intention among Bangladeshi consumers thus enabling the e-commerce businesses to make significant modifications to attract consumers to conduct online shopping. Deduced from prior studies, it is to be noted that there are several factors influencing consumers to use B2C e-commerce services in Bangladesh of which privacy, trust, payment security, delivery, and price are crucial.

1.2 Daraz Bangladesh

Daraz Bangladesh is a leading e-commerce company in Bangladesh that offers its customers considerable online shopping opportunities as well as an online showroom for its vendors. Daraz was established in 2012 and is the preferred online marketplace for South Asia. It is now conducting business in South Asian nations including Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, and Nepal. Its marketplace features 30,000 vendors and 500 brands, and its 5 million users may choose from 2 million goods. It was able to dominate the market by being the first movers. Consumer electronics, home furnishings, clothing, consumables, cosmetics, and sporting items are just a few of the products available on Daraz. Additionally, it provides a variety of payment methods, including cash-on-delivery. After acquiring the online marketplace Daraz in May 2018, Chinese internet giant Alibaba increased its presence in Bangladesh, a move that changed the e-commerce environment in Bangladesh. Currently, Alibaba Group Holding Limited is the owner of Daraz.

1.3 Significance and Methodology of the Study

While e-commerce adoption is a well-established research topic in developing countries, this issue is addressed by only a few researchers in Bangladesh. Smartphones have taken everything into the consumer's hands and online shopping is getting trendy in Bangladesh. The E-commerce Association of Bangladesh (E-Cab) and the trade body

for e-commerce in Bangladesh estimate there are 700 e-commerce sites and around 8,000 e-commerce Facebook pages in Bangladesh. People enjoyed endless searching options, comparing prices, home delivery, and most importantly personalization on e-commerce portals, to the point that many businesses made their web platforms for online consumers. Daraz.com.bd is one of them.

Daraz Bangladesh has a great opportunity, and the company is convinced that emerging markets will multiply in the next few years. So, analyzing the factors that influence consumers' purchase intention is the most significant concern for Daraz Bangladesh. This paper focuses on the factors influencing the purchase intention of Daraz.com.bd. Privacy and returning policies gradually become very important factors in determining consumers' purchase intention, so the current study includes these two factors as well to explore their relationships with consumer satisfaction in the context of Bangladesh's E-commerce.

The study aims to investigate the variables that affect Bangladeshi customers' desire to purchase on the B2C e-commerce platform Daraz.com.bd. Primary and secondary data from multiple Bangladeshi sources are collected for this purpose. To better identify the elements influencing e-commerce customers' purchasing intentions, the questionnaire was made available to Bangladeshi internet users. The research questions were generated prudently before conducting a pilot test with 20 participants. The pilot test is done to gather preliminary data and to conduct a reliability test to make sure the questionnaires are reliable and valid. The leading survey was then conducted by involving 302 Bangladeshi internet and Daraz.com.bd users. After gathering the primary information from 302 respondents, a validity test was employed to evaluate the model's construct, which included ten factors related to e-commerce usage intention, including privacy, payment security, trust, price, quality, social influence, delivery, customer service, return policies, and purchase intention. After the validity test, a co-relationship test and regression analysis were carried out. Following the regression analysis, an interaction test was run to tell whether any of the variables may have been indirectly related or had a combined impact on the dependent variable. Figure 2. illustrates the research map.

Figure 2: Research Map

1.4 A Literature Review on E-commerce and Online Purchase Intention

The adoption of e-commerce in developing countries presents different challenges than those in developed countries (Molla & Licker, 2005). The most important factors for e-commerce adoption in developing countries are organizational, technological, and environmental factors (Tornatzky & Fleischer, 1990). The finding of Dixit and Dutta (2010) depicted that acceptance of e-commerce services by Indian customers is influenced by many factors such as security and privacy, trust, familiarity, and awareness. Arun (2013) found that in the case of online shopping, previous online purchasing experience, purchasing intention, and online trust have significant effects on buyer purchasing intention. According to Hasbullah (2016), recommendations from friends and family are helpful when making an online purchase.

With a GDP growth rate of above 7%, Bangladesh's economy is regarded as one of the world's fastest-growing major economies. According to Ahammad et al. (2017), Bangladesh must develop and use e-commerce technologies for the nation to advance. Customers who shop online in Bangladesh are happy to do so and are more likely to do so in the future (Jubayer, 2015). Online shopping allows consumers to compare costs and search for various items to assist them in deciding which item(s) to buy (Hoque, 2014). Consumers are paying increasing attention to e-commerce since it offers benefits such as reduced transportation costs, the ability to shop from anywhere at any time, and quick access to a selection of items (Qazi, 2014). Consequently, consumers and marketers may contribute significantly to the country's economy through e-commerce.

Customer satisfaction is described as a post-evaluation of buying decisions (Churchill Jr. & Surprenant, 1982). To continue using the e-commerce platform, consumers need to trust that they are offered better products and services than other alternatives (Bhattacharjee, 2001a). Consumers' channel-choice behavior is studied in the service outputs model by Bucklin (1972), who argues that channel services exist and remain profitable through the quality of service and benefits to consumers. Although satisfaction is a behavioral approach that affects consumers' purchase intention, e-commerce platform preference is a choice of consumer behavior that is based on their previous experience (Coughlan et al. 2001), and consumer preferences differ with the shopping experience (Heilman et al., 2000). A range of B2C success stories demonstrate that customer service provided before and after the purchase is necessary for e-commerce consumers' repeated purchases (Shanker et al., 2000).

According to Warshaw and Davis (1985), intention to purchase is an advance plan for the future purchase of specific services or products. The intention shows that consumers will assess perceived quality from their experience and they search for information through preference and the external environment, evaluate the alternative, and make a purchase decision in the final stage (Zeithaml, 1988; Dodds et al., 1991).

Consumers' expectations of payment security and safety have significant effects on their online purchase intention (Limayem et al., 2000). Online retailers must create further convenience for their consumers by reducing the delivery time and increasing the product and customer service quality (Coughlan et al., 2001). The study by Hoque et al. (2015) demonstrates that perceived usefulness is a significant factor in describing the user's adoption of e-commerce and that security concerns and privacy aspects are crucial issues that hinder the adoption of the system. Asghar and Stephen (2013) found that security and privacy are the main barriers to e-commerce adoption. Increased security could prevent potential damages from unreliable exchanges, hacking, or reduced access control to essential information (Hesson & Alameed, 2007). Fram and Grady (1995) found that most concerns consolidated into collecting business transaction issues such as lack of security and a lack of alternative payment options. Security concerns notably affect the individual choice to buy from the Internet (Yang & Jun, 2002). Salisbury (2001) found that perceived security is a much stronger determinant of the intention to purchase online than the website's perceived ease of use and utility. Likewise, Miyazaki and Fernandez (2001) showed that the rate of online product purchases is highly related to the perceived security control possessed by a website. Islam et al. (2011) found security and privacy are substantial factors in the adoption of m-commerce services.

Due to the lack of face-to-face interaction between the buyer, the consumer, and the product, the sense of customer trust is significantly reduced in online shopping (Cho et al. 2007). Trust concerning online shopping includes confidence in abstract systems, technically or socially (Sydow, 1998). Trust is an essential factor influencing consumer behavior, and it determines the success of technology adoption such as e-commerce (Holsapple and Sasidharan, 2005). According to Palvia (2009), trust has a significant effect on purchase intention through usage attitude. Building trust between two parties is crucial for companies that do business online (Chawdhry et al., 2002; Chew, 2007; Luarn and Lin, 2005; Petre et al., 2006). Vaidyan (2008) found in his study that functional and security factors in web design have a significant impact on consumers' trust in e-commerce websites. Barakat & El Sheikh (2010) researched shopping centers in Amman, Jordan and the results indicated that trust and utility have a strong positive influence on new technology acceptance.

The promise of savings is an important motive that attracts consumers to shop online. Zeithaml (1982) proposed that consumers encode and interpret actual prices in ways that are meaningful to them. Therefore, it has been concluded that it is the perceived price, not the actual cost, of a product that affects consumers' product evaluation

and choices (Jacoby & Olson, 1977; Zeithaml, 1988). As per Malc et al. (2016), price fairness has not only influenced the consumers to buy a product but also spread a negative perception about the seller. Some online resources like video blogs changed the consumers' mindset on the physical and social attractiveness of luxury brand perceptions and attitude homophily on para-social interaction (PSI). Lichters et al. (2016) have observed that the compromise effect for buying durable goods is more robust than the fast-moving consumer goods. Alba et al. (1997) pointed out that online shopping enables customers to obtain more information about both price and non-price information as a result of cost search. Since consumers can obtain more online price information and compare it with a few clicks across online retailers, they are likely to shop online when a product's price is high rather than low.

E-service quality is characterized as the degree to which a site encourages productive and successful shopping, purchasing, and delivery (Parasuraman et al., 2005), and it is also crucial for differentiating among electronic commerce (e-commerce) providers and gaining competitive advantage (Benaroch & Appari, 2011; Kim & Lee, 2009; Shaaban & Hillston, 2009). A study found that the most crucial aspect of information quality is the provision of sufficiently current data (Nicolaou & McKnight, 2006). For example, a high degree of variety and timely information about products or services provide online customers with a sense of excitement and helps them make better purchasing decisions (Ahn et al., 2007). Other studies have revealed that Internet shoppers seek updated information about products for stimulation and excitement; although they are satisfied with products they have already purchased (Sorce et al., 2005; Nicolaou & McKnight, 2006).

E-shopping usage has been heavily studied since the emergence of e-commerce in the 1990s. However, relatively insufficient attention has been paid to the effects of logistics on e-shopping behavior, despite the close relationship between them (Wang & Xiao, 2015). Delivery plays a vital role in e-commerce adoption. Final delivery, as the last leg and the most complicated segment of the logistics chain of the B2C delivery chain, is responsible for sending the package(s) at a particular timeslot to a specific place specified in advance, including a transfer of related packages to another destination upon a customer's request, even at the last minute (Gevaers et al., 2014). Essentially, final delivery is the only link in the e-commerce supply chain that involves direct and face-to-face interaction with consumers. The quality of the final delivery service will shape the last impression of the consumer of the entire logistics service and the performance capabilities of the e-retailer (Esper et al., 2003; Boyer et al., 2009; Honeycomb, 2014).

People experience conformity pressures from other members of a social group. The actions of others have a powerful effect on a given member's behavior (Cialdini and Goldstein, 2004). Merely communicating a norm in writing can induce conformity (Darley and Latane, 1967; Von et al., 1999; Parks et al., 2001; Cohen, 2003). For instance, people diverge from other consumers' product choices to ensure that the group makes desirable inferences about their identities (Berger and Heath, 2007). Khalifa and Cheng (2002) conducted a cross-sectional survey study by distributing 220 sets of questionnaires. The results suggested that the perception of an individual's behavioral control and exposure indirectly affects purchase intention. Given the growth of online review websites, marketing scholars have examined the demand consequences of online product ratings (Bickart & Schindler, 2001) and found limited empirical evidence on social influence in online ratings. A possible reason for the mixed evidence is that past research has overlooked the contingent nature of social influence effects in the web rating context. Insights into social influence effects in online product ratings may thus have high managerial relevance.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

Based on the review of relevant research discussed earlier, the following hypotheses were developed and are proposed for analysis in this study to directly address how these factors influence consumers' purchase intention.

H₁: Consumers' needs for privacy negatively affect the intention to purchase online

H₂: Perceived safety of online payment has a positive effect on the online purchase intention

H₃: Trust positively affects purchase intention on the e-commerce platform

H₄: Social influence positively affects online purchase intention

H₅: Price is positively associated with purchase intention.

H₆: Quality positively affects purchase intention

H₇: Returning policy positively affects purchase intention for e-commerce

H₈: Delivery positively affects online purchase intention

2. Research Methodology

The research employs a quantitative approach as it generates numerical data, is inexpensive, fast, and is a simple way to gather information from a more significant number of participants (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Primary data was gathered from the target respondents—users of Bangladesh's Daraz.com.bd e-commerce platform—using survey questionnaires. The survey questionnaire was designed by using the “Wenjuan Xing” survey website. After constructing all the survey questions, a link was created for participants to access, complete, and submit the survey questions. The survey website link was then shared in Bangladeshi WeChat, Facebook, and WhatsApp groups, forums, and via e-mails and private messages to reach 302 targeted respondents who had shopped from the daraz.com.bd at least once. There were a total of 35 questions stated in the questionnaire which took three weeks to reach 302 responses from the targeted users. Submissions not meeting the criteria were disregarded. Certain respondents took less than 90 seconds to submit the survey; this indicated random submission without reading the survey questions thoroughly and was disregarded.

Secondary data was collected from different journals, articles, and books, that are relevant to the research topic and available in the library of Zhejiang Normal University (both paper-based and e-sources such as Science Direct, Google Scholar, Emerald Insight, etc.). Statistical tools SPSS and STATA are used to measure the performance of the data.

2.1 Sampling Design

2.1.1 Target Population

Sampling is a process used in statistical analysis in which a predetermined number of observations are taken from a larger population. To process sampling, it's necessary to choose a small quantity of items from a larger group of elements. Then it's required to analyze the small group of items or people, the outcome of this calculation will assist in calculating the whole population or larger number (Smith & Albaum, 2013).

All adults of Bangladesh nationality (age > 18 years; younger people aren't allowed to open an account) were the target population for this study. Since the study aims to understand better the factors influencing the purchase intention of Bangladeshi consumers to do shopping from the online platform daraz.com.bd, the main focus was on those who purchased at least one thing from Daraz.com.bd.

2.1.2 Sampling Frame and Location

The sampling frame is a list of populations, directories, geography, maps, or other sources used to represent the overall population. Because of the limited time and distance between the researcher and the target population and because survey questionnaires were sent through social media, it was impossible to reach every person in the sampling frame. Therefore, non-probability sampling was selected for this research due to which there is no actual sampling frame. The sampling location is Dhaka City, the capital and the largest city in Bangladesh. The survey questionnaires were distributed to more than 302 target respondents by posting and sharing the questionnaire link through WeChat groups, e-mail, thematic forums, and Facebook, but only 210 people responded. Later on, the questionnaire link was forwarded one by one to people, and 361 responses were collected.

2.1.3 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

The sampling method determines the accuracy of a survey result. Non-probability sampling was selected for this research due to which there is no actual sampling frame.

The sample size chosen for this study was 302 - 302 Bangladeshi nationals above the age of 18 years who will participate in the survey. More than 300 survey questionnaires set were distributed among Bangladeshi people to collect the data. The pilot test was conducted before moving to the actual test. In a research project, a pilot study is one of the most critical stages to detect the actual problems and lack of research instruments and protocols before starting to do the research (Hassan et al., 2006). The pilot test ensures that all survey participants were able to understand the questionnaires and provide correct answers. To conduct a pilot test, the researchers posted a set of 20 survey questionnaires online. It was confirmed that there were no confusing questions, incorrect terms, or grammatical errors in the survey questions.

2.2 Research Instruments and Methods

This study utilizes quantitative methods to assist the author in conducting hypothesis tests and identifying the causality of specific events or circumstances. According to Oxford University Press (2001), using self-administered questionnaires has several advantages, including being reasonably inexpensive for gathering large amounts of data and convenient for participants to respond in their free time at home, allowing for more honest responses. To conduct this study, electronic questionnaires were designed and posted on the Internet and the survey link was shared with the participants through WhatsApp, e-mails, WeChat, Facebook, etc.

2.2.1 Questionnaire Design

Questionnaires are considered one of the most appropriate data-gathering tools to collect data from large samples; this method thus perfectly suits the aim of this study. Burgess (2001) stated that survey questionnaires should include different types of questions; for example, multiple choices versus single-choice responses, closed versus open-ended questions, ranking, and rating. The following types of questions were used in this research:

1. Open-ended questions to get socio-demographic information from the respondents
2. Closed-ended with two or multiple choices for respondents to choose from for a single answer
3. Rating response for the research: The Bipolar Likert scale is used to get responses from participants. The Likert scale was used to measure the behavior and attitude of the respondents. The selected scale has seven choices for the respondents to rate their views on specific questions.

This study includes 35 questions divided into two sections. The two sections of the questionnaire are designed in English and shared with Bangladeshi e-commerce users.

Section I:

There are 7 questions about the demographic information of respondents who participated in the survey. The first five questions are about the name, gender, age, education, and country of residence (control variables being gender, age, and education). The next two questions are for people who have done online shopping in general or from Daraz.com.bd. If participants never did any shopping online or any previous shopping on Daraz.com.bd, then their responses were not accepted. Among these seven questions, two questions are open-ended with a single response, five are closed-ended with only one answer.

Questions about gender, age, nationality, and education were used to build a socio-demographic profile to avoid collecting data from other nationalities. Hawkins (1992) asserted that age is generally regarded as a powerful consumer behavior predictor because the particular age would have an impact on his/her interests and ability to select the most comfortable environment from all the options. The research didn't accept any responses from respondents who were younger than 18 years old (who were unable to open accounts on Daraz.com.bd).

Section II:

The second section has 28 questions directly addressing the research. These questions concentrate on respondents' cognitive and trust indicators- privacy, payment and safety, price, trust, quality, customer service, social influence, returning policy, and purchase intention. These factors are used to understand the purchase intention of Bangladeshi consumers. To measure the participants' attitudes and apprehension towards online shopping from Daraz.com.bd, the seven-point bipolar Likert scale was applied as a rating scale (Table 1) in these 28 questions.

Table 1: Seven-Point Bipolar Likert Scale Rating Scales

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somehow Disagree	Neutral	Somehow Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

2.2.2 Pilot Test

The purpose of the pilot test is to check the survey questionnaire's consistency and reliability to ensure that all the questions are accurate with wording and phrases. 20 sets of survey questionnaires were shared with Bangladeshi Daraz.com.bd users to conduct the pilot test. Following the pilot test and evaluation of the questionnaires' internal consistency, the survey questionnaires were distributed to the target population.

To check the internal consistency of questions, Cronbach's Alpha is commonly used by researchers. The range of Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient is from 0 to 1. The higher the Alpha coefficient scores, the more reliable internal consistency.

George and Mallery (2003) offered the following rules for the Alpha coefficient:

- Cronbach's Alpha > 0.9 "Excellent"
- Cronbach's Alpha > 0.8 "Good"
- Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7 "Acceptable"
- Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6 "Questionable"
- Cronbach's Alpha > 0.5 "Poor"
- Cronbach's Alpha < 0.5 "Unacceptable"

Table 2: Pilot Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Coeff.
Privacy	0.665
Payment and Safety	0.851
Trust	0.777
Price	0.796
Quality	0.962
Customer Service	0.827
Delivery	0.893
Returning policy	0.714
Social Influence	0.823

Table 2 shows the reliability test results of the pilot test. Results demonstrate acceptable and good levels of reliability for all the factors presented in the pilot study.

2.3 Data Analysis Techniques

2.3.1 Descriptive Analysis

SPSS software and Microsoft Excel produced a frequency distribution, chart, and graph to represent the demographic profile of e-commerce consumers in Bangladesh.

2.3.2 Inferential Analysis

Factor Analysis (Structure Detection and Dimension Reduction Methods), Pearson Correlation, and Multiple Regression were executed in the study. The main purpose of factor analysis techniques is to reduce the number of variables and to recognize the structural connections between variables to classify variables. Pearson Correlation

is performed to measure the linear correlation between two variables. Multiple Regression analysis (in STATA) is then done to predict purchase intention and to figure out the most influential factors of the independent variable.

3. Data Analyses and Results

3.1 Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents

The survey questionnaires were distributed online and 361 responses were acquired from the targeted respondents. Fifty-nine participants' data had been deleted as they did not meet the requirements. So, the sample size of respondents became 302.

Table 3: Respondents' Gender

	Frequency	Percent
Male	211	69.87
Female	91	30.13
Total	302	100.00

Table 3 shows that male participants are much more than female participants implying Bangladeshi men use the internet and social media frequently and are more interested in completing survey questionnaires.

Figure 3: Respondents' Age Groups

Figure 3 demonstrates that the bulk of participants (201/302) are between the ages of 18 and 25. The 26–30 age group had the second-highest number of responders (64/302). This indicates that people in the 18–30 age range (87.75%) may be classified as a generation that is interested in the newest technology, uses gadgets and e-commerce technologies more frequently, and has the financial resources to buy technical items. Thus, marketing to a certain age range of individuals will be advantageous.

Figure 4: Respondents' Educational Levels

The majority of respondents who took part in this survey hold an undergraduate degree (figure 4). From this, it's clear that undergraduate and graduate people (264/302) should be targeted for marketing purposes.

3.2 Data Analysis

3.2.1 Reliability Measurement

Table 4 shows that privacy, trust, price, quality, customer service, delivery, returning policy, and social influence factors have Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient above 0.7. The lowest value in the Cronbach's Alpha test is for payment and safety (.635), and the level of internal consistency for it is questionable.

Table 4: Results of Reliability Statistics – Test on independent variables

Cronbach's Alpha	
Privacy	.705
Payment and Safety	.635
Trust	.740
Price	.737
Quality	.721
Customer Service	.705
Delivery	.739
Returning Policy	.746
Social Influence	.766

3.2.2 KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity measures how suited the data is for the Factor Analysis. KMO values of the test range from 0 to 1 and the world-over accepted index is over 0.6 for Factor Analysis; (Cerny & Kaiser, 1977). The result of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity shows the strength of the relationship among variables, and it indicates the compatibility and validity of the responses collected.

Table 5: Adequacy of each variable

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Measure of Sampling Adequacy	0.801
Bartlett's	Approx. Chi-Square	1907.296
Test of Sphericity	df	190
	Sig.	.000

The KMO test indicated a 0.801, which is a meritorious, excellent result, meaning that all the items within the model to measure dimensions fully capture the dimensions and are sufficient to support the hypotheses. The significance of Bartlett's Sphericity Test is below 0.05 with a result of 0.000 implying that the variables support the model fittingly.

3.2.3 Total Variance Explained

The Total Variance Explained supports the four dimensions of the research.

Table 6: Total Variance Explained after Dimension Reduction

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Rotation Sums of Squared Loading		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.076	25.382	25.382	2.153	10.766	10.766
2	2.376	11.878	37.260	2.081	10.405	21.171
3	1.563	7.815	45.075	2.040	10.200	31.371
4	1.485	7.424	52.498	2.018	10.092	41.463
5	1.158	5.788	58.286	1.924	9.620	51.083
6	1.081	5.403	63.689	1.914	9.571	60.654
7	.977	4.883	68.572	1.584	7.918	68.572
8	.795	3.974	72.546			
9	.719	3.595	76.141			
10	.650	3.249	79.390			
11	.536	2.682	82.072			
12	.505	2.525	84.597			
13	.458	2.289	86.886			
14	.435	2.176	89.062			
15	.427	2.136	91.198			
16	.419	2.093	93.291			
17	.389	1.944	95.234			
18	.362	1.808	97.042			
19	.301	1.506	98.548			
20	.290	1.452	100.000			

Table 6 lists the eigenvalues for the reduced model associated with each linear component before and after extraction and rotation.

Extraction sums before rotation are marked in bold amongst all initial eigenvalues. Before extraction, 20 linear components were identified within the new data set, which is equal to the amount of the remaining independent variables in the adjusted model. All factors with eigenvalues greater than 0.9 are extracted, which leaves seven components for the revised model.

The rotation has the effect of optimizing the factor structure. Before rotation, factor 1 accounted for considerably more variance than the remaining six (25.382% compared to 11.878%, 7.815%, 7.424%, 5.788%, 5.403%, and 4.883%), although, after extraction, it accounts only 10.766% (compared to 10.405%, 10.200%, 10.092%, 9.620%, 9.571 and 7.918% respectively). Compared to the initial set of variables, the amount of justified data increased from 63.69% to 68.572%.

3.2.4 Rotated Component Matrix

The Rotated Component Matrix shows how many factors are to be analyzed. In this case, seven out of nine- social influence (SI), delivery (D), price (PR), returning policy (RP), privacy (P), quality (Q), and trust (T). It can be seen that the items are not interfering with each other. Therefore, the components can measure purchase intention well.

Table 7: Validity Test and Factors Loading

	Component						
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
SI1	.762						
SI2	.832						
SI3	.754						
D1		.742					
D2		.758					
D3		.752					
PR1			.771				
PR2			.853				
PR3			.713				
RP1				.778			
RP2				.822			
RP3				.683			
P1					.787		
P2					.820		
P3					.738		
Q1						.738	
Q2						.810	
Q3						.622	
T1							.815
T2							.818

The factor analysis supports the seven factors model; all the factor loadings are above the acceptable level of 0.6 which means that the proposed model has good construct validity (Qian et al., 2018) and SPSS can distinguish the seven variables.

3.2.5 Pearson Correlation Coefficient

The correlation is defined by describing the degree of relationship between two variables or how two variables linearly co-relate with each other (Tiemann, 2010). In this study, Pearson correlation analysis was carried out to examine the relationship between independent variables.

Table 8: Pearson Correlation

		PAV	TAV	PRAV	SIAV	RPAV	QAV	DAV
PAV	Pearson Correlation	1						
TAV	Pearson Correlation	-.128*	1					
PRAV	Pearson Correlation	.008	.215	1				
SIAV	Pearson Correlation	.035	.209**	.259**	1			
RPAV	Pearson Correlation	-.026	.220**	.378**	.426**	1		
QAV	Pearson Correlation	-.239**	.435**	.259**	.275**	.320**	1	
DAV	Pearson Correlation	-.201**	.411**	.233**	.318**	.294**	.502**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Correlation coefficients (table 8) show that the independent variables have a moderate relationship. However, since none of the bivariate correlations of independent variables is more than 0.70 (Tabachnick & Fidell, 1996), all the variables meet the requirements for the regression analysis.

3.2.6 Linear Regression Analysis

Regression in the current study includes explanatory or independent variables- privacy, trust, price, social influence, returning policy, quality, and delivery- to predict the value of the dependent or response variable (purchase intention). According to Neri (2010), human behavior is inherently noisy and therefore it is not always possible to produce accurate predictions, but multiple regression allows researchers to identify a set of predictor variables that will altogether provide a useful estimate of a participant's possible score on a criterion variable. Multiple regression, compared to simple linear regression that only allows one dependent and one independent variable, allows for any number of independent variables – k independent variables to potentially be related to the dependent variable. The model in this study is as follows:

$$y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_kx_k + e \quad (1)$$

where y represents the dependent variable (PI), x the independent variables ($x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k$), b is the Coefficient, and e the random errors.

VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) measures the impact of collinearity among the variables in a regression model, and the acceptance level is below 10.

According to Table 9, there exists significant relationships between the factors and the dependent variable.

Table 9: Regression Coefficients

	Coefficients	t	Sig.	VIF
Age	.041	.430	.668	1.443
Gender	.014	.089	.929	1.039
Education	.228	1.903	.058	1.437
Privacy	-.153	-2.735	.007	1.141
Trust	.160	2.620	.009	1.382
Price	.168	2.562	.011	1.226
Quality	-.038	-.504	.615	1.583
Delivery	.271	3.741	.000	1.544
Returning Policy	.230	3.312	.001	1.427
Social Influence	.365	5.387	.000	1.320

The Adjusted R square is 0.591 for the model, which means the linear regression explains 59.1% of the variance in the data which is very close to the acceptable minimum of 0.6. Because the coefficient values are below 0.29, privacy, trust, price, quality, delivery, and returning policy have a weaker but significant influence, while social influence with a value of 0.365 has a medium influence on purchase intention. After including all demographic variables, a significant effect of independent variables on the dependent variable still exists. The demographic variables are seen to be insignificant. Social influence is the most significant and the most influential in purchasing intention. VIF values prove that the seven factors significantly impact the dependent variable. The independent variables privacy, trust, price, quality, delivery, returning policy, and social influence are free from multicollinearity issues.

3.2.7 Regression Coefficient Interaction Test

In practice, the test of interaction effect measures which factor is the most significant regarding purchase intention whether the independent variables (seven) have an impact on one another, and if so, which factors are enhancing or weakening the other in influencing purchase intention (Dodge, 2003).

The effect of Privacy and Price (PxPR), Privacy and Quality (PxQ), delivery, and social influence (DxSI) have adverse interaction effects on the dependent variable, purchase intention, even though separately, all these factors affect the purchase intention positively. The interaction between Privacy and Social influence (PxSI), Quality and Social influence (QxSI) enhance one another's positive effect on purchase intention. The rest of the interaction terms do not have a significant effect on purchase intention among Bangladeshi consumers.

Table 10: Regression Coefficient Interaction Test

PI	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Age	.0412863	.0883494	0.47	0.641	-.1325986	.2151712
Gender	.0136391	.1581288	0.09	0.931	-.2975821	.3248603
Edu	.2284175	.1219095	1.87	0.062	-.0115186	.4683537
Privacy	-.1529155	.0491097	-3.11	0.002	-.2495709	-.0562602
Trust	.1598992	.070682	2.26	0.024	.0207864	.299012
Price	.1680503	.0718578	2.34	0.020	.0266234	.3094771
Quality	-.0380081	.087875	-0.43	0.666	-.2109593	.1349431
Delivery	.2707588	.082298	3.29	0.001	.1087841	.4327336
RP	.2302971	.0672103	3.43	0.001	.0980173	.362577
Social I	.3649688	.0728905	5.01	0.000	.2215094	.5084283
PxT	-.0325198	.0409312	0.79	0.428	-0.480521	.1130918
PxPR	-.0789367	.0380202	-2.08	0.039	-.1537784	-.004095
PxQ	-.1604922	.0684271	-2.35	0.020	-.295189	-.0257953
PxD	.068345	.0669283	1.02	0.308	-.0634016	.2000915
PxRP	.0532691	.0423199	1.26	0.209	-.0300365	.1365747
PxSI	.0742652	.0377606	1.97	0.050	-.0000654	.1485959
TxPR	.0557525	.061193	0.91	0.363	-.0647043	.1762093
TxQ	-.086595	.0629179	-1.38	0.170	-.2104472	.0372572
TxD	.0133497	.0644928	0.21	0.836	-.1136026	.140302
TxRP	.093074	.0554936	1.68	0.095	-.0161636	.2023115
TxSI	-.0885264	.0660265	-1.34	0.181	-.2184978	.0414449
PRxQ	.040486	.0344727	1.17	0.241	-.0273725	.1083446
PRxD	.0790558	.0541867	1.46	0.146	-.0276092	.1857207
PRxRP	-.1071574	.0595113	-1.80	0.073	-.2243038	.009989
PRxSI	.0472087	.0661845	0.71	0.476	-.0830737	.1774911
QxD	.0384938	.0579558	0.66	0.507	-.0755905	.1525781
QxRP	-.0100205	.0672451	-0.15	0.882	-.1423907	.1223496
QxSI	.1601852	.0660489	2.43	0.016	.0301698	.2902005
DxRP	-.000521	.0653167	-0.01	0.994	-.129095	.1280531
DxSI	-.1617298	.0764954	-2.11	0.035	-.3123089	-.0111508
RPxSI	.0456391	.0432307	1.06	0.292	-.0394594	.1307375
_cons	2.020842	.2674862	7.55	0.000	1.494303	2.547381

3.3 Hypotheses Evaluation

H₁: The regression analysis indicated the negative impact of privacy requirements on the dependent variable, purchase intention. Purchase intention will drop as privacy expectations rise. The interaction test results showed that privacy and price combined had a significant negative impact on purchase intention as well. Similarly, the interaction between privacy and quality has a combined significant negative impact on Bangladeshi e-commerce customers' inclination to make a transaction. As such, **H₁** is supported.

H₂: During the total variance test, the factor payment and safety items were extracted that are subject to the factor analysis. It was noted during secondary data collection that e-commerce consumers prefer to have cash on delivery instead of payment online. Besides that, the online payment system is very complicated and insecure in Bangladesh. Thus, **H₂** is rejected by this study.

H₃: The regression analysis clarified that the trust factor doesn't have a significant effect on the online purchase intention of Bangladeshi consumers. Therefore, **H₃** is rejected by this study.

H₄: The findings from regression analysis proved this hypothesis to be true. Furthermore, privacy and social influence combined positively affect the online purchase intention of Bangladeshi consumers. Quality -social influence interaction term positively affects the purchase intention as well. Therefore, **H₄** is supported.

H₅: It is proved from the regression analysis that the price positively and significantly influences the purchase intention of the e-commerce platform in Bangladesh. Thus, **H₅** is also accepted through this study.

H₆: The regression analysis showed that quality has no significant impact on purchase intention among Bangladeshi online shoppers. However, the interaction term for quality and social influence positively affects the purchase intention. Thus **H₆** can be accepted to an extent.

H₇: The study demonstrates that returning policy significantly and positively affects the dependent variable. If the e-commerce platform retains a returning policy, then consumers will be more comfortable buying from that platform. As a result, the purchase intention rises. **H₇** is consequently supported.

H₈: The findings from regression analysis show that delivery positively influences the dependent variable purchase intention thus making **H₈** acceptable.

4. Conclusion

This study provides sufficient evidence from a practical point of view that can be useful for the branding, marketing, and promotion of domestic e-commerce service providers in Bangladesh. The paper aimed to provide a scenario for the factors that determine the purchase intention of Bangladeshi nationals on the Daraz.com.bd e-commerce platform. Nine key factors were included to conduct the whole research study— privacy, payment, and safety, trust, price, quality, delivery, customer service, returning policy, and social influence. The results showed that privacy, trust, price, quality, delivery, returning policy and social influence had a statistically significant influence on purchase intention. Consumer purchase intent will rise if Daraz.com.bd gains more credibility, prices are lowered to more affordable and acceptable levels, delivery times are shortened, and return policies are made easier. Among all the variables, social influence appears to be the one that has the greatest impact on Bangladeshi consumers; as a result, online ratings and reviews are a developing form of interpersonal communication that is not only out of a company's control but also a significant influence on consumer purchasing decisions. The results may prove valuable for online retailers and marketers in Bangladesh and other emerging nations.

Although this research attempted to provide a considerable amount of both theoretical and practical contributions, future research could address certain limitations posed by the study. Firstly, this research adopted a random sampling technique. All the respondents of this study came via social media platforms. Hence, the sample may not reflect the entire population. Secondly, only nine factors were represented as independent variables and only seven of them had a significant influence on the dependent variable. Consequently, the existence of other factors that the research could not take into account cannot be ruled out. Those factors might have a significant impact on the purchase intention and including them in further studies may give different outcomes. Thirdly, this research focused on one e-commerce website Daraz.com.bd, the most popular platform in Bangladesh. The result may vary from site to site and product to product. Although the interaction effect between the elements was only looked at for further explanation, instead of giving answers, it just raised more questions, which might be a reasonable basis for another new research topic. Further research is desirable to address and overcome the mentioned limitations and shortcomings.

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